

THE PECULIARITIES OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN AMERICAN ENGLISH

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Abstract: *This article explains the distinctive qualities of phraseological units in American English and how they are used in figurative and metaphorical phrases. Linguists have also conducted research on the topic of English phraseology.*

Keywords: *phrase, compound, phraseological, grammatical, expression*

Introduction: Phraseology—a term derived from the Greek terms phrasis, which means "expression," and logic, which means "doctrine"—is the most significant area of linguistics, which focuses on phraseological structure. First things first, one must have a greater comprehension of what phraseological units are. Phraseological units are collections of several words with a consistent structure (it is not re-formed every time, but is used in a ready form). Consequently, a phraseological unit always appears as a single component of the sentence in the analysis of a phraseological unit, regardless of its type or the number of words it includes.[1:97]

Phraseology is a relatively new field of research that focuses on the analysis of diverse stable compounds. & W. Weinreich, L.P. Smith, and A. McKay are English linguists. In other words, phraseologies are a distinct unit of language that comprise figurative, fixed word combinations that are structurally comparable to a free link or sentence, completely or partially semantically rebuilt. Phraseological combinations are just word combinations. Phraseological combinations, or phraseologies, are a distinct unit of language that include figurative, fixed word combinations that are structurally equivalent to a free link or sentence, fully or partially semantically reconstructed. Phraseologies are a subset of language that includes these fixed word combinations. Most of the idioms have unclear origins and unknown authors, having been developed by speakers of both English and other languages. In this regard, the phraseologist A.V. Kunin, who is obscure but is the creator of several English phraseologies, correctly noted that they were developed by individuals.[2:65] Yet, it is possible to identify the roots of some phraseological units. In this regard, phraseology may be thought of as a microsystem that is a component of the larger system of language and that reflects the history and traditions that have been passed down from one generation to the next. Many phraseological components that make up a system are sources of linguistic enrichment for a given language. The link between phraseological units and their primary components makes up the phraseological system. Phraseologisms are word

combinations with more than one word that are consistent in form and meaning. Phraseologisms are employed figuratively, have historical use norms and conventions, and their meaning is made clearer by a particular speech act. Whether they take the shape of a phrase or a sentence, phraseologisms are distinct from sentences that constitute a unit of speech. They resemble words in many respects as a lexical unit, and phraseology has many of the same traits with words. Phraseological units are language constructions with a single meaning that are characterized as being structurally stable.[3:87] It was proposed by MN Shansky and SN Ivanov that the term "Modern language" should be restricted to independent word combinations and words on the one hand, and to words on the other. As a result, while translating, phraseological units with meanings comparable to those in other languages are frequently used. For instance, the phrase "keep your fingers on the pulse," which literally means "keep your fingers on the pulse," makes more meaning when translated as "be aware of happenings." The phrase "keep your finger on the pulse" has taken its place instead because there isn't a completely equivalent phrase in Russian. Phraseology goes through its own stages of genesis and evolution, much like other areas of linguistics. The study of phraseology has been studied for about 200 years, despite the fact that its roots are very old. Charles Bani, a physicist from Switzerland, is credited with creating phraseology. While Ferdinand de Saussure expressed his opinions on syntagma and its characteristics, he included special chapters on the study of word combinations in his book *French Stylistics* (1909).[4:76] Due to their meaning and syntactic properties, he claimed that such compounds are used in a ready-made, according to tradition.

For instance, the play's hefty father; the phrase "kick the bucket" when someone dies; and red tape. - Phraseologisms have a single meaning when used together, such as the bureaucratic technique. A phrase's meaning has totally changed due to phraseological misunderstanding. Yet, unlike phraseological compounds, their meanings cannot be inferred from those of their constituent parts.[5:65]

Phraseologisms known as phraseological compounds are comprehended from the phraseological meaning of a phraseology as a whole. Migration of meaning based on metaphors is transparent and straightforward. The most consistent expressions are those found in phraseological compounds' lexical parts. For instance: to ride a high horse (to act in a superior, haughtily, or arrogant manner); to look a gift horse in the mouth (to analyze someone critically; to find fault with something one obtained without work); to be a large bug; to be a fish out of water (a person situated uncomfortably outside his usual or proper environment) Phraseological units are crucial building blocks for evoking emotion, expression, and imagery, and they improve the expressive potency of writings written by artists for the public. Phraseologisms are the result of extensive evolution and reflect societal experience, passing it down from one generation to the next. As a result, they serve as both a communication tool and a repository for a variety of socially valuable data. In this view, the national cultural semantics of a language is the outcome of historical

evolution, which also incorporates the cultural past; the richer a nation's history, the more vibrant and diversified its linguistic units' content will be. The comparative study of the pharmacology of various languages helps to improve awareness of the behavior, culture, literature, history, and customs of those who speak these languages as well as the structure of both languages. The study included a variety of research techniques, including associative, conceptual, contextual, component, lexicographic, linguocultural, semantic-cognitive, and etymological analysis. [6:109]

Outcomes and analysis of such results. It is crucial to understand what a phraseological unit is before considering the nature of phraseological units.

There are several theories for defining phraseology's object. Phraseology solely deals with stable compounds as its subject. The study of phraseological units' structural characteristics, their placement in the linguistic system, and the characteristics of their use at a particular time is known as phraseology. The spiritual culture, traditions, professions, way of life, history, ambitions, and perspective on reality of the language's speakers are all intimately connected to phraseological units. The study of phraseological units is a topic that has received a lot of attention in global linguistics. Although the origins of phraseological units are very old, the history of phraseology as a discipline spans over two centuries.

Charles Balli was the pioneering investigator of phraseological theory. He incorporated distinct chapters on the analysis of phraseological units into his scholarly writings. Phraseological compounds are mostly made up of word combinations; in other words, phraseologies are distinct linguistic units that comprise figurative, fixed word combinations that have undergone full or partial semantic transformation and are structurally equivalent to free links or sentences. The majority of phraseologies have unclear origins and unidentified authors, having been developed by speakers of both English and other languages. This is how phraseological expert A.V. As the majority of contemporary English idioms are unattributed, it has been logically suggested that humans invented them. Certain phraseological units, nevertheless, may be traced back to specific origins. In this way, phraseology may be seen of as a microsystem that is a component of the larger system of language and that reflects the history and traditions that have been passed down from one generation to the next. The system's phraseological components often serve as sources of linguistic enrichment for a given language. The link between the phraseological units' primary components makes up the phraseological system.

Phraseologisms are word linkages that have more than one word in them and are stable in form and meaning.

Conclusion

Phraseological units, with their concision, impact, and semantic weight, match the ethos of the time. This in turn demonstrates once more the current relevance and significance of phraseological study. The resources gathered and their analysis can be applied to the literary translation process, English lexicology lectures, hands-on

training, and dictionary compilation. Moreover, using the findings of this research, functional and semantic studies may be conducted on words and phrases from additional lexical-semantic groupings. The knowledge of the culture, literature, history, and traditions of the people who speak these languages is enriched by comparative studies of phraseology, which give a greater grasp of both languages' structures.

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